

Phonological Domains in Martuthunira
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Primary Source(s)

Alan Dench. 1995. *Martuthunira: a language of the Pilbara Region of Western Australia*.
ANU: Pacific Linguistics

I. Notes on syllable structure: CV(:)C

All Martuthunira syllables/words **must** begin with a consonant and **may** end in a consonant or vowel. Permissible initial consonants are restricted to the peripheral and laminal stops and nasals, and the peripheral and laminal glides /w/ and /y/. Final consonants are chosen from among the apical nasals and laterals, the lamino-palatal nasal and lateral, and the trill /rr/. All vowels may occur in word-final position.

All lexical roots in Martuthunira are at least bimoraic. Bimoraic roots may be monosyllabic, in which case they are V; or disyllabic (CV.CV). A number of morphemes have different forms depending on the number of morae in the stem to which they are attached. In all cases, such 'mora-counting' alternations are sensitive to a basic contrast between bimoraic stems and stems of more than two morae.

Super heavy syllable of the type CV:C, can be stem final (or perhaps at the end of word + reduplicant in this reduplication example):

- (1) paarn**paarn** silly (rn = apico post-alveolar nasal)

II. P-Rules & Processes, and the Morpho-Syntactic Information they Reference

Intramorphemic consonant clusters consist of no more than two consonants and fall into two classes: a set of heterorganic clusters of different kinds, and a full set of homorganic nasal-stop clusters (there are no homorganic lateral-stop clusters). The set of consonants which may occur as the first member of a heterorganic cluster corresponds to the set of consonants permitted in word-final position. The second member of such a cluster is drawn from the set of peripheral consonants plus the palatal glide /y/; that is, a subset of the consonants permitted in initial position. These look like clusters that cross syllable boundaries.

- (2) wil**p**ilpi emu chick [wil.pil.pi]
kuril**k**ura seagull (= Ngarluma)

Intermorphemic clusters: The possibilities for consonant clusters at morpheme boundaries are very open and can be characterised in the most general terms as

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involving one of the permissible word-final consonants followed by a permissible word-initial consonant. A few morphemes that may be suffixed to consonant final stems violate the usual constraints on word initial consonants. Two different strategies are employed to avoid non-permissible clusters that would otherwise arise in this situation. Firstly, the syllable /**pa**/ (following a final nasal) or /**wa**/ (following a lateral or the alveolar rhotic) is inserted preceding the clitic -rru.

- (3) pirtan-**pa**-rru minthal-**wa**-rru
 quartz-Ø-NOW alone-Ø-NOW

Secondly, an epenthetic vowel /**u**/ is inserted between a stem-final /l/ or /n/ and the clitics -l, -lwa and -nu. Similarly, the clitics -lwa or -nu following clitic -l are separated by /**u**/:

- (4) minthal-**u**-lwa pirtan-**u**-nu mir.ta-l-**u**-lwa
 alone-Ø-ID quartz-Ø-QUOT not-THEN-Ø-ID

As a general tendency, **stops** are voiceless and unaspirated in word-initial position and following a nasal, and voiced between vowels. However, there is a degree of free variation in voicing for all stops in all positions. Firstly, the peripheral stops /p/ and /k/ are most often voiceless, even between vowels. Similarly, the alveolar stop /t/, which is rare in intervocalic position, is always voiceless and involves a longer period of closure than is usual for other stops in this position.

By contrast, the apico-postalveolar stop /rt/ is realised as a (voiced) retroflex flap [ɽ] between vowels and both apical stops tend to be voiced following a nasal. The laminal stops are usually voiced in intervocalic position with the interdental /th/ showing the greatest tendency to lenition. This stop is variously realised as a voiced interdental stop [ɸ], a dental fricative [θ], or as an interdental glide [ɣ]. The variation appears to be partly determined by the particular lexical item.

Laterals are articulated with slight pre-stopping where they close a syllable:
pal.ya [p^lly] 'skinny'

The alveolar **rhotic** /rr/ is realised as a tap [ɾ] between vowels and as a trill [r] in final position, where it is usually voiceless. Preceding a consonant both tap and trill articulations are heard.

Vowels

Unstressed positions have a centralising effect on vowels.

Lenition of peripheral stops

Allomorphs of a number of morphemes show evidence of a conditioned alternation affecting the velar stop /k/. Firstly, the stop is lenited to a laminal glide /y/ following a stem-final lateral or the alveolar rhotic /rr/.

- (5) Accusative suffix: jinkarn-**ku** mukul-**yu**

By contrast, the 'belonging' suffix shows lenition of /k/ to /w/ where /y/ is predicted:

- (6) jinkarn-kura mukul-wura

Similar lenition of morpheme-initial /k/ to /w/ occurs following a vowel-final stem. Thus the genitive has three forms:

- ku on stems with a final nasal
-yu on stems with a final lateral or rhotic
-wu on stems with a final vowel
(7) muyi-wu jinkarn-ku
 pawulu-wu kanparr-yu

On vowel-final stems the lenition of the accusative suffix extends to loss of the consonant

and harmonising of the suffix vowel with the final vowel of the stem:

- (8) muyi-i dog-ACC
 pawulu-u child-ACC

Morphophonemic lenition of the bilabial stop /p/ to the glide /w/ is shown by a number of reduplications:

- (9) parra-warra

Deletion of one of two similar syllables

A number of morpheme combinations result in the dropping of one of two similar syllables.

The 1st such pattern affects the 2nd syllable of the passive derivational suffix -CM-nguli-Ø when followed by certain final verb inflections. Here a syllable /li/ is dropped when the following syllable begins with a lateral or the alveolar rhotic /rr/:

- (10) *-nguli-layi > -ngu-layi
 -PASS-FUT
 *-nguli-lu > -ngu-lu
 -PASS-PURPss

A similar pattern involves the dropping of the final /rri/ syllable of the collective (a) and 'body-noise' (b) derivational suffixes preceding the contemporaneous relative inflection -rra:

- (11) (a) -marri-rra > -marra -yarri-rra > -yarra
 (b) -karri-rra > -karra

This reduction is optional. Unreduced versions are occasionally heard in text and are

usually given in careful response to elicitation.

Mora counting allomorphs

The clearest cases of mora counting alternation involve the locative and effector nominal suffixes. These morphemes follow the common Australian pattern with forms -ngku/a and -lu/a on vowel-final stems. The -ngku/a allomorph occurs on nominal stems of two morae while the -lu/a alternant occurs on all stems of more than two morae.

- | | | |
|------|-------------|--------------|
| (12) | nguu-ngka | face-LOC |
| | kaara-la | hip bone-LOC |
| | nharnu-ngka | sand-LOC |
| | malarnu-la | shade-LOC |

Similarly, the 'full-laden' suffix, -warlaya, has a shortened form -warla which appears on bimoraic stems:

- | | | |
|------|-----------------|-----------|
| (13) | murti-warla | fast-FULL |
| | marrari-warlaya | word-FULL |

Finally, there are different forms of the collective suffix on L-conjugation verbs depending on the length of the verb stem. On a stem of just two morae the suffix has the form -yarri-Ø while on longer stems the suffix is -lwarri-Ø:

- | | | |
|------|-------------------|---------------|
| (14) | karta-yarri-Ø | stab-COLL |
| | thuulwa-lwarri-Ø | pull out-COLL |
| | thani-yarri-Ø | hit-COLL |
| | kartatha-lwarri-Ø | chop-COLL |

Stress

At the lexical level, all morphemes of more than a single syllable in length have stress on their first syllable. In addition, the monosyllabic verbalisation suffixes -ma-L and -tha-L have lexical stress (stress is indicated by underlining).

- | | | |
|------|--------------------|---------------------|
| (15) | <u>p</u> anyu | good |
| | <u>k</u> anyara | man, person |
| | - <u>m</u> ulyarra | -ALLative |
| | - <u>ma</u> -L | -CAUSative |
| | - <u>tha</u> -L | -Controlled Contact |

It is necessary to recognize three levels of stress assignment.

- 1) morphemes bear a lexical stress mark.
- 2) regular phonological stress rules modify the patterns arising from the combination of stress-marked morphemes in accordance with a general ban on sequences of two stressed syllables or sequences of three unstressed syllables.
- 3) the preferred word-stress patterns may be modified by the marking of emphatic

stress at the phrase level.

- 1) At the lexical level, all morphemes of more than a single syllable in length have stress on their 1st syllable.
- 2) The stress patterns arising from the combination of lexically stressed morphemes are modified by regular rules. The rules remove stress marking from the 2nd of adjacent stressed syllables, and add stress to any syllable flanked by two unstressed syllables. By convention the rules operate from left to right.

Rule 1 **CV** Æ CV/**CV** __

Rule 2 CV Æ **CV**/CV__CV

- (16) **pa**nyu-rri-rra-rru lexical stress
panyurri-rra-rru Rule 2
- (17) **nh**artu-**ma**-rninyji lexical stress
nhartu**ma**rninyji Rule 1
- (18) **wa**nthami-**ma**-rninyji-rru lexical stress
wantham**ma**rninyji-rru Rule 1
wantham**ma**rninyji-rru Rule 2

Long vowels also affect stress placement: stress is removed from the 2nd of a pair of adjacent stressed syllables where either involves a long vowel.

Rule 3 **CV(V)** Æ CV(V)/**CV(V)** __

- (19) **ng**urra-**a**rta
ngurra**a**rta

The preferred stress patterns of words are often affected by phrase stress and intonation patterns, syntactic emphasis on particular morphemes, and metrical rhymes. First, there is a tendency to stress final case-markers in certain contexts; usually where some contrast in syntactic function is being emphasised. Second, word stress assignments which result in word-final stress occurring on the antepenultimate syllable may be modified so that stress falls on the penultimate syllable. This shift most often occurs where a word has five syllables. A 3+2 metrical stress pattern is generally preferred over a 2+3 pattern. (I don't understand what it means)

- (20) **pa**tha-**rra**lha-rru Æ **pa**tharra**lh**arru
kanarri-lha-rru Æ **ka**narr**il**harru

Finally, the expected stress pattern for a word may be modified so that it 'rhymes' with the stress patterns of other words in a phrase.

Compounds: Words which are recognisable as **compounds** (even though their component morphemes do not necessarily occur as free forms in modern

Martuthunira) have a stress pattern in accord with their component morphemes. For example:

- (21) Mangkuru(+)thuni Peter Creek
Wangkarta(+)muka Mount Mistake

Reduplication

Reduplication, not a particularly productive morphological device in Martuthunira, involves the complete reduplication of the lexeme root. Trisyllabic reduplications are relatively uncommon and appear more to resemble words in apposition than true reduplications, the two parts of a trisyllabic reduplication bear an intonation pattern and degree of relative stress more in keeping with their being separate words.

- (21) jampa-jampa near to death
witha-witha lost
manha-manha shaky
winyarta-winyarta exhausted

Lenition of stops discussed above (part of reduplication):

Word-initial /p/ and /k/ are replaced by /w/ in medial position.

- (22) kurryu- wurryu bumpy
kulha- wulha heaped up

This lenition is part of a general historical process affecting intervocalic peripheral stops. However, the rule does not appear to be general for all reduplications. For two words in the data the lenition is optional.

III. Available Morpheme Types

stem

suffix

enclitic/post-posed particle